

Call 2 report on dissemination activities

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Authors: Ona Tribó, Jordi Malapeira, Teresa Monserrat, Sònia Sánchez.

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D3.3 CALL 2 REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

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Project no. 101126533

TOUCH

Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH

MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)

Start date of project: 01/02/2024 Duration: 60 months

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1. Report on dissemination activities

The second call for applications for the TOUCH doctoral programme was open from 1 February to 31 March 2025. In the months leading up to and during the call period (January–March 2025), significant communication and dissemination efforts were carried out to maximise outreach and ensure broad visibility among potential candidates and relevant stakeholders.

Communication activities included the publication of targeted announcements on the project's official website and social media platforms (LinkedIn, X/Twitter, and Instagram), and the dissemination of promotional materials through academic and professional channels. In addition, the call was featured in several institutional newsletters and relevant online portals dedicated to research and innovation opportunities, including EURAXESS.

Partners actively contributed to the promotion of the call by sharing the information within their institutional and professional networks, thus ensuring international coverage and attracting a diverse pool of applicants from different disciplines and geographic regions.

1.1. Website

The TOUCH website serves as the main communication and information hub of the programme. It provides comprehensive and up-to-date details about all key aspects of the action, including the overall description of the doctoral programme, the participating organisations, and the research areas covered. It also hosts the most relevant documentation related to the recruitment process, such as information about open calls, the Guide for Applicants, FAQs, application platform and Helpdesk contact details to support potential candidates throughout the application period.

For the second call, the website played a central role in ensuring transparency, accessibility, and effective communication. A dedicated section was created to highlight the call, featuring detailed information on eligibility criteria, application procedures, evaluation and selection process, and key dates.

To maximise visibility, updates and reminder were regularly published on the news section. The website also provided downloadable resources, including the required templates and official documents, to guide applicants through each step of the submission process.

In addition, the website was integrated with the project's social media channels, ensuring consistency in communication and driving traffic from external platforms. Analytics from the period of the call indicate a significant increase in website visits, reflecting the strong engagement generated by the promotional campaign.

Through this comprehensive online approach, the TOUCH website effectively served as the central access point for all information and updates related to the second call, supporting an open, fair, and well-informed recruitment process in line with the principles of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions.

1.2. Social media

A coordinated social media campaign was implemented across multiple platforms, including LinkedIn, Instagram and X/Twitter. The campaign aimed to maximise visibility and engagement among researchers and potential applicants across Europe and beyond.

Visual materials were designed specifically for each platform to ensure consistent branding and adaptability to different formats. To facilitate unified communication, a document containing suggested post texts and hashtags was prepared and shared with all the implementing partners, encouraging them to publicise the call via their institutional accounts. All partners used the hashtag #TOUCHprogramme, which allowed the campaign's impact to be tracked and amplified in a coordinated way.

Additionally, the call was actively promoted via the official [TOUCH LinkedIn page](#), with multiple posts published throughout the application period. These posts included visuals, key dates and direct links to the call details on the project website to ensure that prospective candidates could easily access information.

Overall, the social media campaign significantly contributed to raising awareness of the second TOUCH call, ensuring broad outreach and reinforcing the project's visibility across academic and research networks.

	X/Twitter	LinkedIn	Instagram
Posts	13	15	6
Impressions	16.912	236.153	1.528

1.3. Info Day

The TOUCH Info Day, a virtual event designed for prospective doctoral candidates, was held on 10 February 2025. The session aimed to present the wide range of opportunities offered by the TOUCH Doctoral Programme and to provide detailed information about the second call for applications.

The one-hour online event, which started at 10:00 CEST, was structured in two main parts. The first segment featured a comprehensive presentation by the Project Manager, who introduced the programme’s objectives, research areas, training components, eligibility criteria and selection process. This was followed by an interactive Q&A session, where participants were able to ask specific questions about the application process, selection criteria, and fellowship conditions.

The Info Day was widely promoted through the project’s official website and communication channels, including social media platforms, ensuring broad outreach among potential candidates and academic networks.

The event successfully raised awareness of the TOUCH doctoral programme and encouraged participation in the second call, fostering engagement from a diverse international audience of early-stage researchers interested in pursuing high-level interdisciplinary research within the TOUCH consortium.

The Info Day video was uploaded on Youtube: [TOUCH Info Day](#)

TOUCH Info Day	
Nº of registrations	121
Nº of participants	79
Nº questions by attendees	23
Nº views of the uploaded video	268

1.4. News

Two dedicated news items were published on the TOUCH project website to announce the launch of the [second call](#) for doctoral candidates (on 17 January 2025) and the [TOUCH Info Day](#) (on January 16 2025). These news pieces provided essential information about the programme and the call timeline, while also inviting potential applicants to join the Info Day for further insights into the programme and the recruitment process.

To maximise visibility and outreach, the announcements were also featured on the UAB's institutional website and disseminated through all partners' websites. Each consortium partner adapted the content to their local context and audiences, sharing it across their communication channels, including newsletters, news sections, and social media platforms.

This coordinated communication effort contributed to increasing the visibility of the TOUCH doctoral programme and ensuring wide dissemination across academic, research, and professional communities at international levels.

1.5. EURAXESS

The TOUCH doctoral programme announced its second call for applications through the EURAXESS platform on 21 January 2025. The publication served as a key channel to reach an international audience of early-stage researchers and ensure broad visibility across the European Research Area.

The EURAXESS job announcement provided comprehensive and structured information to guide potential candidates through the application process. It included a detailed overview of the predoctoral programme, outlining the research areas, training activities, and mobility opportunities offered within the consortium. The post also described the partner institutions, eligibility criteria, employment conditions, and selection procedure, ensuring transparency and clarity for applicants. Moreover, the publication featured clear instructions on how to submit applications via the official TOUCH website, directing candidates to the online submission platform and providing relevant deadlines and documentation requirements. The EURAXESS advertisement remains publicly accessible through the following link: [EURAXESS Post](#).

In addition to the general TOUCH programme announcement, each of the 21 projects offered in the second call was published individually on the EURAXESS portal on 21-22 January 2025. These individual postings included not only the general programme and selection process information but also a detailed description of the specific research project, supervisors, research group, and the required skills and qualifications for a competitive application. Additional details about the EURAXESS publications, including individual links to each doctoral position offered under this call, are available in Deliverable D3.2.

EURAXESS
Researchers in motion

Home Jobs & Opportunities Living & Working in Europe Career Development Initiatives Network ERA Talent Platform

You are here: Home > Jobs & Opportunities > Job offer

Job offer

UAB
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

JOB SPAIN

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona | Posted on: 21 January 2025

11 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)

[Apply now](#) [Share](#)

PAGE CONTENTS

- [Job Information](#)
- [Offer Description](#)
- [Where to apply](#)
- [Requirements](#)
- [Additional Information](#)
- [Work Location\(s\)](#)

STATUS: EXPIRED

 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

21 JAN 2025

Job Information

Organisation/Company	TOUCH
Research Field	Psychological sciences Neurosciences Sociology Demography

1.6. Email campaign

During the last week of January 2025, an email campaign was launched to disseminate essential information about the second call for doctoral candidates and the TOUCH Info Day.

The campaign was distributed to a carefully selected audience, including relevant mental health associations and networks, as well as our extensive international network of partners and EU-funded projects related to the programme's thematic area.

The main objective of the mailing campaign was to maximise the number of international applicants by implementing a targeted digital communication strategy. The campaign aimed to reach highly qualified early-stage researchers and relevant organisations in the field of mental health and related disciplines.

Email campaign	
Total opens	1326
Total clicks	159

View this email in your browser

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

2nd Call of TOUCH doctoral programme

Towards the next generation of excellent young doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approach

Touch
Mental Health & Wellbeing

2nd OPEN CALL
11 doctoral positions

TOUCH is a new excellent doctoral programme led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) for the recruitment and training of doctoral researchers in the field of mental health and wellbeing.

The second call opens from 1 February to 31 March offering 11 doctoral positions under four major thematic areas:

- Fostering mental health and wellbeing across lifespan
- Transdisciplinary approach to mental health & wellbeing determinants
- Multilevel strategies for assessment and intervention in mental health & wellbeing, from genomics to personomics
- Governance in mental health systems: participation, education, and community

What does TOUCH offer?

- Over 20 **opportunities** to undertake research projects with renowned supervisors.
- 3-year full-time contract** (37.5 hours / week) and a gross salary of **2.375 €/month** (the salary will be the same for the 3 years)
- The availability of world class **research infrastructures**
- An **excellent training programme**, including practical hands-on schools, training in research diversity and scientific and communication skills, international and/or intersectoral secondments at partner laboratories and premises.

Join the TOUCH Info Day

Join us on 10 February 2025 for the **TOUCH Info Day**, an online session for doctoral candidates to explore the opportunities provided by the TOUCH doctoral program. Learn more about the call and get answers to your questions about the application process.

Touch

Online Info Day

10 February 2025 | 10:00 h CEST

[Register now >](#)

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